

MATEMATIKA O'QITISH METODIKASINING METODOLOGIK ASOSI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada matematika o'qitish metodikasining metodologik asosi va matematik ta'limning maqsadi, mazmuni, formasi, uslubi va uning vositalari haqida so'z boradi. Maqola davomida asoli fikr va mulohazalardan foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: matematika o'qitish metodikasi, metodika, matematika tizimining butunligi.

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF MATHEMATICS TEACHING METHODOLOGY

Abstract. This article talks about the methodological basis of mathematics teaching methodology and the purpose, content, form, style and means of mathematics education. Reasonable opinions and comments are used throughout the article.

Key words: mathematics teaching methodology, methodology, integrity of the mathematics system.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ МЕТОДИКИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ МАТЕМАТИКИ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о методических основах методики преподавания математики, а также о цели, содержании, форме, стиле и средствах математического образования. На протяжении всей статьи используются обоснованные мнения и комментарии.

Ключевые слова: методика преподавания математики, методика, целостность математической системы.

Matematika o'qitish metodikasining metodologik asosi bilish nazariyasiga asoslangandir. Matematika metodikasi fani matematik ta'limning maqsadi, mazmuni, formasi, uslubi va uning vositalarini dars jarayoniga tatbiqiy qonuniyatlarini o'rganib keladi. Matematika fani fizika, chizmachilik, kimyo va astronomiya fanlari bilan ham uzviy aloqada bo'ladi.

Matematika fanining boshqa fanlar bilan uzviy aloqasi quyidagi ikki yo'l bilan amalga oshiriladi:

1) matematika tizimining butunligini buzmaganda qo'shni fanlarning dasturlarini moslashtirish;

2) boshqa fanlarda matematika qonunlarini, formulalarini teoremlarni o'rganish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan materiallardan matematika kursida foydalanish. Hozirgi vaqtda matematika dasturini boshqa fanlar bilan moslashtirish masalasi ancha muvaffaqiyatli hal qilingan.

Masalan, funksiyalar va ularni grafik tasvirlash haqida fizikada foydalaniladigan ba'zi ma'lumotlarni o'quvchilar VII sinfdan boshlab o'rgana boshlaydilar. VIII sinfdan beriladigan geometrik yasashlarga doir ko'p bilimlar chizmachilik fani uchun boy material bo'ladi, chizmachilikning vazifasi bu bilimlarni turli chizmachilik ishlarini bajartirish yo'li bilan puxtalashdan iboratdir. Matematika metodikasi fani matematik ta'limning maqsadi, mazmuni, formasi, uslubi va uning vositalarini dars jarayoniga tatbiqiy qonuniyatlarini o'rganib keladi.

Matematika fani fizika, chizmachilik, kimyo va astronomiya fanlari bilan ham uzviy aloqada bo'ladi.

Matematika so'zi qadimgi grekcha — *mathema* so'zidan olingan bo'lib, uning ma'nosi «fanlarni bilish» demakdir. Matematika fanining o'rganadigan narsasi (obyekti) materiyadagi mavjud narsalarning fazoviy formalari va ular orasidagi miqdoriy munosabatlardan iborat. Hozirgi davrda matematika fani shartli ravishda ikkiga ajraladi: 1) elementar matematika, 2) oliy matematika. Elementar matematika ham mustaqil mazmunga ega bo'lgan fan bo'lib, u oliy matematikaning turli tarmoqlaridan, ya'ni nazariy arifmetikadan, sonlar nazariyasidan, oliy algebradan, matematik analizdan va geometriyaning mantiqiy kursidan olingan elementar ma'lumotlar asosiga qurilgandir. Oliy matematika fani esa real olamning fazoviy formalari va ular orasidagi miqdoriy munosabatlarni to'la hamda chuqur aks ettiruvchi matematik qonuniyatlarini topish bilan shug'ullanadi. Elementar matematika fani maktab matematika kursining asosini tashkil qiladi. Maktab matematika kursining maqsadi o'quvchilarga ularning psixologik xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda matematik bilimlar sistemasini ma'lum usul (metodika) orqali o'quvchilarga yetkaziladi. (Metodika so'zi grekcha so'z bo'lib, «yo'l» degan ma'noni anglatadi.) Matematika metodikasi pedagogika va didaktika fanining asosiy bo'limlaridan biri bo'lib, jamiyatimiz taraqqiyoti darajasida ta'lim maqsadlariga mos keluvchi matematikani o'qitish, o'rganish qonuniyatlarini o'rganadigan mustaqil fandır.

Matematika o'qitishning umumta'limiy maqsadi o'z oldiga quyidagi vazifalarni qo'yadi:

a) o'quvchilarga ma'lum bir dastur asosida matematik bilimlar tizimini berish. Bu bilimlar tizimi matematika fani to'g'risida o'quvchilarga yetarli darajada ma'lumot berishi, ularni matematika fanining yuqori bo'limlarini o'rganishga tayyorlashi kerak. Bundan tashqari, dastur asosida o'quvchilar o'qish jarayonida olgan bilimlarining ishonchli ekanligini tekshira bilishga o'rganishlari, ya'ni isbotlash va nazorat qilishning asosiy metodlarini egallashlari kerak;

b) o'quvchilarning og'zaki va yozma matematik bilimlarini tarkib toptirish. Matematikani o'rganish o'quvchilarning o'z onalarida xatosiz so'zlash, o'z fikrini aniq, ravshan va lo'nda qilib bayon eta bilish malakalarini o'zlashtirishlariga yordam berishi kerak. Bu degan so'z o'quvchilarning har bir matematik qoidani o'z onalarida to'g'ri gapira olishlariga erishish hamda ularni ana shu qoidaning matematik ifodasini formulalar yordamida to'g'ri yoza olish qobiliyatlarini atroflicha shakllantirish demakdir;

d) o'quvchilarni matematik qonuniyatlar asosida real haqiqatlarini bilishga o'rgatish. Bu yerda o'quvchilarga real olamda yuz beradigan eng sodda hodisalardan tortib to murakkab hodisalargacha hammasini fazoviy formalari va ular orasidagi miqdoriy munosabatlarni tushunishga imkon beradigan hajmda bilimlar berish ko'zda tutiladi. Bunday bilimlar berish orqali esa o'quvchilarning fazoviy tasavur qilishlari shakllanadi hamda mantiqiy tafakkur qilishlari yanada rivojlanadi.

2. Matematika o'qitishning tarbiyaviy maqsadi o'z oldiga quyidagilarni qo'yadi:

a) o'quvchilarda ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirish. Bu g'oya bilish nazariyasi asosida amalga oshiriladi;

b) o'quvchilarda matematikani o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishlarni tarbiyalash.

Ma'lumki, matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning o'qishning dastlabki kunlaridanoq mustaqil ravishda xulosa chiqarishga o'rganadilar. Ular avvalo kuzatishlar natijasida, so'ngra esa mantiqiy

tafakkur qilish natijasida xulosa chiqaradilar. Ana shu chiqarilgan xulosalar matematik qonuniyatlar bilan tasdiqlanadi.

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